

REVIEW OF LITERATURE – SHITAPITTA W.S.R URTICARIA**Patil S.*¹, Zarekar D.², Shinde S.³, Jadhav S.⁴, Jagtap N.⁵**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: *Shitapitta* is one of the *ayurvedic* skin disorders which is characterized by itching, skin eruptions in form of maculo-papular rashes, pricking pain. This is due to vitiation of *vata*, *kapha dosha* associated with *pitta dosha*. *Shitapitta vyadhi* resembles to Urticaria in modern prespective. **Objective:** This review of literature describes *Nidana*, *Samprapti*, *Purvarupa*, *Rupa* and *Chikitsa* of *Shitapitta* by various *Acharyas* and co relate with modern science. **Methods:** Classical *Ayurvedic* texts – *Madhav nidana*, *Yog Ratnakara*, *Bhaishajya Ratnawali* along with modern literature. **Conclusion:** *Ayurveda* gives a holistic approach in managing urticaria through *shitapitta chikitsa* principles.

KEYWORDS: *Sheetapitta*, Urticaria, Skin disorders, *Shodhana*, *Shamana*.

INTRODUCTION

Shitapitta is one of among many skin disorders explained in *samhitas*. It was 1st explained by *Laghutrayis Acharya Madhavakara*, *Yogratnakara* in *samhitas*. *Sheetapitta* word is made from two words *shita* and *pitta*; where the *shita* suggest of *vata* and *kapha dosha* while the *pitta* suggests of *pitta dosha*. Vitiated *vata pradhana dosha* combines with *pitta dosha* spreads internally and externally resulting in *Shitapitta Vyadhi*.^[1] According to modern science, *shitapitta* is compared to urticaria.

Urticaria is a vascular reaction pattern charcterised by transient, erythematous, oedematous papules or wheals of varying sizes and shapes which all usually pruritic. It is also called as hives, nettle rash and wheal. Around 20% of population suffers this condition once in a lifetime. Clinically, there are wheals of varying sizes and shape transient, well defined, erythematous or pale swellings of the dermis. They stay upto 12 hours. No

marks are left behind when the wheals resolve. They are pruritic and stinging with pricking sensation. Use of Nsaids, aspirin, codeine and opioids; Ingestants like nuts, eggs, fish, milk; Inhalants like pollen, house dust, animal dander; Injectants like vaccine, serum, blood; Contactants like cosmetics and animal-plant products; Physical urticaria is due to heat, cold, pressure, solar, aquagenic; Systemic conditions like thyroid disorders, polycythemia vera. The main goal of managing urticaria is to identify and then remove the offending agent/cause. Avoid use of Nsaids as it can aggravate urticaria. Soothing calamine lotions and cold compresses relief pruritis. Antihistamine drugs is main line of treatment. In chronic urticaria, non-sedating antihistamines, h2 blocker, mast cell stabilizer, systemic glucocorticoids are very beneficial.^[2]

Understanding the disease, its etiology, pathogenesis, symptomatology and treatment protocol is important to unfold all the aspect about *shitapitta* disease.

2. NIDANA^[1]

शीतमारुतसंस्पर्शत् प्रदुष्टौ कफमारुतौ |पित्तेन सह सम्भूय
बहिरन्तर्विसर्पतः || १||

NIDAN PANCHAKA

1. SHITAPITTA NIRUKTI

शीतप्रभावात् पित्तदोषप्रकोपेन उत्पन्नो व्याधिः

Table No. 1: *Nidana Of Shitapitta.*

Aharaja Hetu	Viharaja Hetu	Nidan Arthakara Hetu	Chikitsa Mithya Yoga
Santarpana Atilavana Sevan Atiamla Sevan Viruddha Aahar Sevan Tikshna Madya Sevan Katu Sevan Kshara Sevan Adhyasana Guru Dravya Sevan Snigdha Bhojan Sevan Dadhi Sevan Vish Yukta Annapanasevan	Sheeta Marut Sparsha Vishayukta jal Snana Vishayukta Abhanga Vishayukta Udvartana Vishyukta Vastra Vishakta Abhushhana Vishakta Keeta Damsha Bahya Krimi Chhardi Nigraha Atidiwaswap Shishir Rutu Varshakala	Sannipatika, Pittaja And Kaphaja Jwara Unmarda Adhoga Amlapitta	Vamana Ayoga Virechana Ayoga Sweda atiyoga Raktarshe dushta rakta nighraha

3. SAMPRAPTI^[1]

Samprapti is understanding the process of development of disease by the vitiated doshas that constantly circulate throughout the body.

The *samprapti* of *Sheetapitta – Udarda – Kotha* was 1st explained by *Madhavakara* in *Madhava Nidana*.

Due to *Sheeta – Maruta Samsparsha*(exposure to cold air) there is vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha* doshas gets associated with *Pitta Dosha* results in *Bahir Antah Visarpataha* (circulates all over the body internally and externally) causing *Sheetpitta -Udarda- Kotha*.

4. SAMPRAPTI GHATAKA^[1]

Table No. 2: *Samprapti Ghataka.*

<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Tridosha – Vata, Pitta, Kapha</i> <i>Pitta – Bhrajaka Pitta</i>
<i>Dushya</i>	<i>Rasa</i> <i>Rakta</i>
<i>Agni</i>	<i>Agnimandhya</i>
<i>Doshagati</i>	<i>Vridhhi</i> <i>Tiryaka</i> <i>Shakha</i>
<i>Vyadhi Marga</i>	<i>Bahya</i>
<i>Strotas</i>	<i>Rasavaha</i> <i>Raktavaha</i>
<i>Strotas Dushti Prakara</i>	<i>Vimarga Gamana</i>
<i>Udbhava Sthana</i>	<i>Amashaya</i>
<i>Vyakti Sthana</i>	<i>Twaka</i>
<i>Swabhava</i>	<i>Ashukari</i>

5. PURVAROOPA^[3]

Purvaroopa is the group of signs and symptoms seen before onset of any disease.

In *shitapitta* they are seen as follows.

पिपासारुचिहल्लासदेहसादाङ्गौरवम् |रक्तलोचनता तेषां
पूर्वरूपस्य लक्षणम् || २||

Table No 3: Purvarupa Of Shitapitta.

Pipasa	Thirst
Aruchi	Anorexia
Hrillasa	Oppression in chest
Dehasada	Debility
Anga Gauravam	Heaviness of body
Rakta Lochanata	Reddness of eyes

6. RUPA^[4]

Rupa is the group of signs and symptoms seen after manifestation of disease.

In *shitapitta* they are seen as follows.

वरटीदृष्टसंस्थानः शोथः सञ्जायते बहिः
 |सकण्डुस्तोदबहुलश्छर्दिज्वरविदाहवान्||३||
 उदरमिति तं विद्याच्छीतपित्तमथापरे |वाताधिकं
 शीतपित्तमुदरस्तु कफाधिकः||४||

Table No. 4: Rupa Of Shitapitta.

Vartidashtasamsthana Shotha	Skin eruption which are elevated resemble like a sting of wasp
Kandu	Severe itching
Toda	Pricking pain
Chardi	Vomiting
Jwara	Fever
Daha	Burning sensation

7. CHIKITSA

Whenever we think of *chikitsa* related to any disease, they can be divided in following aspects.

1. *Nidana Parivarjana*

Nidana is the causative factor of disease and avoiding the causative factor is main and primary line of treatment.

In case of *shitapitta* disease, it is formed by internal and external *nidanas* and avoidance of both *nidanas* are important.

2. *Samprapti Vighatana*^[5]

For *samprapti vighatana*, we have 3 types based on extent of vitiation of *doshas*.

Table No 5: Chikitsa According To Dosha Awastha.

Heena Dosha Awastha	Langhana
Madhyama Dosha Awastha	Langhana – Pachana (Shamana)
Bahu Dosha Awastha	Shodhana

3. *Pathya – Apathya*

Pathya is synonym of *chikitsa*. Drugs and regimen that do not adversely affect the body and mind. While the drugs and regimen which adversely affected mind and body is called as *Apathya*.

Almost all *acharya* has explained that line of treatment of *shitapitta* must be done under line of treatment of following disorders.

1. *Krimi Dadru* 2. *Kushta* 3. *Amlapitta*

Management of *Sheetapitta* in Ayurveda.^{[6][7][8]}

Chakradutta	Based on doshagati
Bhavaprakasha	Shodhana Shamana Bahi parimarjana
Yoga ratnakara	Krimighna drugs Dadrughna drugs

Shaman Chikitsa

Mineral drugs - *Parad, Swarna, Loha, Trama, Abhraka, Kasis, Gandhak, Gairik, Praval & Shanka*

Charkokta gana^[9]– *rasayana, kushtagna, varnya* and *kandughna*

Shodhana Chikitsa^{[8][10]}

In *Laghutrayis, Sheetapitta* is treatment is explained as follows.

Table No. 6: Shodhana Chikitsa In Shitapitta.

Vamana	<i>Bhajshajya Ratnawali</i>	<i>Patol Patra + Nimba Patra + Madanphal Kwath</i>
	<i>Yoga Ratnakar</i>	<i>Patol + Nimba Saal + Vasa Kwatha</i>
Virechana	<i>Yoga Ratnakar</i> <i>Bhaishajya Ratnawali</i>	<i>Triphala + Suddha Guggulu + Pippali</i>
Raktamoskshana	<i>Yoga Ratnakar</i>	<i>As Rakta Pradoshaja Vikara and Rakta Dushti</i> <i>Raktamoskshana is Advised after Mahatiktak Ghrita</i>
Abhyanga	<i>Yoga Ratnakar</i> <i>Bhaishajya Ratnawali</i>	<i>Katu Taila</i>
	<i>Bhaishajya Ratnawali</i>	<i>Yavakshara + Saindhava + Sarshapa Taila</i>
Lepa	<i>Bhaishajya Ratnawali</i>	<i>Durva + Haridra</i>
	<i>Madhava Nidana</i>	<i>Saindhavadi Yoga – Kustha + Saindhava Mixed</i> <i>With Ghrita</i>
Udvartana	<i>Yoga Ratnakar</i>	<i>Kushtadi Churna – Kustha + Haridra +</i> <i>Daruharidra + Sursa +Patol+ Shigru+ Nimba+</i> <i>Ashwagandha+ Devdaru+ Sarshapa+ Tejbalphal+</i> <i>Takra</i>

KALPA ON SHEETAPITTA^{[6][7][8][10][11][12]}

Table No 7: Kalpa In Shitapitta.

Bhavprakash	<i>Navakarshika Guggulu</i> <i>Trikatu Sharkara</i> <i>Yavani Vyosha Yavakshara</i> <i>Aardraka Rasa Purana Guda</i> <i>Yavani Guda</i> <i>Guda Amalaki</i> <i>Nimba Patra Ghrita Amalaki</i> <i>Ardraka Khanda</i>
Bhaishajya Ratnawali	<i>Visarpokta Amritadi Kwatha</i> <i>Agnimantha Moola Ghrita</i> <i>Yashtyadi Kwatha</i> <i>Amratadi Kwath Goghrita</i> <i>Maricha Vardhamana Prayoga</i> <i>Haridra Khanda</i> <i>Brihat Haridra Khanda</i> <i>Shleshmapittantako Rasa</i> <i>Veereshvaro Rasa</i> <i>Sheetapitta Bhanjan Ras</i> <i>Vardhamana Pippali</i> <i>Vardhamana Lasuna</i> <i>Kushathadi Churna</i> <i>Vardhman Lashuna</i> <i>Guduchi Dhamasa Nimba Nisha Kwath</i>
Charaka Samhita	<i>Udarda Prashamana Mahakashaya</i> <i>Katu Tail</i> <i>Mustadi Churna</i>
Chakradatta	<i>Visarpokta amritadi kwatha agnimantha moola +</i> <i>ghruta shushka pakva gambhari phala after boiling with milk</i>
Sushruta Samhita	<i>Eladi Gana</i>
Yog Ratnakar	<i>Vardhamana Pippali</i> <i>Vardhamana Lasuna Prayoga</i>

8. PATHYA – APATHYA

Sheetapitta has a major role of pathya and apathya as they can act as a hetu – 100ausative factor.

So studying the do's and don't's is important.

Table No 8: Pathya – Apathya In Shitapitta.

	AHARA	VIHARA
PATHYA	<i>Jeerna shali</i> <i>Jangala mamsa</i> <i>Triphala</i> <i>Dadima phala</i> <i>Vetragra phala</i> <i>Karkotaka shaka</i> <i>Karavellaka shaka</i> <i>Shigru shaka</i> <i>Potika shaka</i> <i>Madhu</i> <i>Ushnodaka</i> <i>Mudga yusha</i> <i>Kulattha yusha</i> <i>Moolaka yusha</i> <i>Lava rasa</i> <i>Tittira rasa</i>	<i>Langhana</i> <i>Abhyanga</i>
APATHYA	<i>Ksheera vikarani</i> <i>Ikshu vikarani</i> <i>Anupa – audaka mamsa</i> <i>Matsya</i> <i>Viruddha ahara</i> <i>Guru annapana</i> <i>Naveen madhya</i>	<i>Chardi nighrahana</i> <i>Diwaswapna</i> <i>Snana</i> <i>Atapa sevana</i> <i>Purva and daksheena direction air</i> <i>Vyavaya</i>

DISCUSSION

Shitapitta is a multifactorial disorder involving systemic imbalance rather than a purely dermatological issue. The *Ayurvedic* explanation of dosha involvement aligns with modern concepts of immune hypersensitivity and inflammatory mediators.

Unlike modern treatment, which focuses on antihistamines and symptomatic relief, *Ayurveda* emphasizes root cause management through detoxification and lifestyle correction. This holistic approach may offer long-term benefits and reduce recurrence.

However, scientific validation through clinical trials is needed to establish the efficacy of *Ayurvedic* therapies. Integrative research combining traditional knowledge and modern diagnostics could provide better treatment strategies.

CONCLUSION

In modern science, urticaria and other allergic skin disorders has wide range of treatment but the reoccurrence is very common. In *ayurvedic* science, urticaria is compared to *shitapitta*. It is most common *twaka vikara*. *shitapitta* is mainly caused due to exposure to *asatmya ahara* and *vihara*. This *asatmya ahara* and *vihara* hampers the immunity resulting in interaction with allergens easily. *Ayurvedic* treatment has major role in *shitapitta* giving cost effectivity and patient centered outcomes. It includes the *panchakarma* with lowers the *vata* and *pitta doshas* by *vaman*, *virechana*, *raktamokshana*, local acting *panchakarma* is *lepa*, *abhyanga*, *udvartana* has best results reducing the

shotha, *daha* and *toda*. It does have many *kalpas* explained with *pathya – apathya Kalpana*.

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